

EFFECT OF CORRECTION OF DYSBACTERIOSIS ON THE COURSE OF DIABETES MELLITUS

*Katamadze N.,
Kandashvili T.,
Metreveli D.,
Khutsishvili L.*

Georgia. Tbilisi State Medical University

ABSTRACT

In the last 20 years, many studies have been conducted worldwide to study the causes and prevalence of diabetes. According to population studies, the majority of new cases of diabetes mellitus are not detected at an early stage and a large proportion of cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus are undiagnosed. There is a wide variety of medications available today for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. Many of them, despite the many side effects, e.g. Sulfonylureas are still actively used because they have a powerful hypoglycemic effect. Diabetic complications are the leading causes of disability, mortality and poor quality of life. Studies have established that obese patients, those with insulin resistance, have a characteristic intestinal microflora - usually an increased ratio of *Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes* compared to the healthy population. Due to the relevance of the issue, the aim of our research was to study the improvement of carbohydrate metabolism in patients with type 2 diabetes by restoring intestinal flora.

Glycated hemoglobin was evaluated in the study group before and after treatment. According to the results in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, glycated hemoglobin decreased by 0.24% on the background of unchanged antidiabetic therapy, while in the control group it increased by 0.36%. Statistical processing of qualitative and quantitative data was carried out, which allowed us to determine that there is a reliable positive correlation between the two variables (values obtained before treatment and as a result of treatment). Compared to the control group, where glycated hemoglobin did not decrease.

Keywords: Diabetes type 2, probiotics, microbiome.

In the last 20 years, many studies have been conducted worldwide to study the causes and prevalence of diabetes. According to population studies, the majority of new cases of diabetes mellitus are not detected at an early stage, and a large proportion of cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus are undiagnosed [1] Prediabetes is not less dangerous, because the risk of developing diabetes and cardiovascular system diseases increases in the early stage, i.e. against the background of impaired glucose tolerance.

There is a wide variety of medications available today for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. Many of them, despite the many side effects, e.g. Sulfonylureas are still actively used because they have a powerful hypoglycemic effect. Other classes of drugs: e.g. Metformin, which remains the first-line, so-called As the drug of choice for the treatment of type 2 diabetes, incretins and new generation SGLT2 inhibitors are actively used, since they have been found to have other positive effects on the cardiovascular system.

Diabetic complications are the leading causes of disability, mortality and poor quality of life [9][10] Complications in people with diabetes can develop in different organs and manifest differently. Complications of diabetes mellitus, especially in type 2 diabetes, are quite common and as we have already mentioned, at the time of diagnosis, most of the patients have at least one complication.

The scientists are looking for alternative ways, which, in addition to existing medications, would provide proper treatment of diabetes, thus avoiding the risk of developing complications.

The intestinal barrier/permeability plays a critical role in the development of obesity and type 2 diabetes [6] The intestinal epithelium is a barrier, its main function is to limit the interaction of intestinal microflora, the local immune response and other parts of the body. The integrity of the intestinal barrier maintains the

function of the mucosa, which is very important in the formation of defense mechanisms [7] According to animal studies, lipopolysaccharides are also involved in the regulation of processes related to diabetes mellitus, which are characterized by the enhancement of the inflammatory responses [4]

Studies have established that obese patients, those with insulin resistance, have a characteristic intestinal microflora - usually an increased ratio of *Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes* compared to the healthy population [3] Also, altered intestinal microflora in obese people increases the production of metabolic endotoxins [2] which leads to a sluggish chronic inflammatory process, which is the cause of the pathogenesis of insulin resistance. Over time, insulin resistance becomes the reason for the development of type 2 diabetes.

Due to the relevance of the issue, the aim of our research was to study the improvement of carbohydrate metabolism in patients with type 2 diabetes by restoring intestinal flora.

58 patients with type 2 diabetes with gastro-intestinal disorders were selected, who underwent a study of the intestinal microflora before and after treatment with probiotics by bacteriological examination of stool, and 12 patients of a control group with type 2 diabetes, who also underwent a study of the intestinal microflora, but they were not given probiotics.

The research material was the data obtained in the study group before treatment and as a result of treatment and in the control group according to the following indicators: *bifidum bacteria*, *lactic acid bacteria*, *enterococci*, *intestinal sticks (typical)*. The statistical study of bacteriological data showed that the mean rate of *lactic acid bacteria*, *bifidum bacteria* and *enterococcus* in the study group increases, while it remains unchanged in the control group.

Changes in *lactic acid bacteria*, *bifidobacteria* and *enterococci* in the study group

The patients of the research group were given a complex of probiotics: (*Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Bifidobacterium breve*, *Bifidobacterium longum*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus lactis ssp.Lactis*, *Streptococcus thermophilus- 20 X10⁹*) 2 caps. 3 times a day or 6 caps. a day for 12 weeks.

Glycated hemoglobin was evaluated in the study group before and after treatment. According to the results in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, glycated

hemoglobin decreased by 0.24% on the background of unchanged antidiabetic therapy, while in the control group it increased by 0.36%. Statistical processing of qualitative and quantitative data was carried out, which allowed us to determine that there is a reliable positive correlation between the two variables (values obtained before treatment and as a result of treatment). Compared to the control group, where glycated hemoglobin did not decrease.

Changes in glyated hemoglobin in the study group and control group

Characteristics	Min.	Max.	Mean	Standard deviation	Median
Study group- before treatment	6,8	9,1	7,8	0,48	7,9
Study group- after treatment	6,7	9	7,8	0,47	7,9
Control group- before	7,4	9,4	8,4	0,66	8,4
Control group- after	7,5	9,4	8,4	0,65	8,4

Against the background of treatment with probiotics, the bacteriological analysis of feces was dramatically improved, the number of lactobacilli and bifidobacteria was completely restored. No similar change was observed in the control groups.

In patients with type 2 diabetes, on the background of unchanged antidiabetic treatment, using probiotics for 3 months, the reduction of glyated hemoglobin by 0.24% can be explained by the following mechanisms: first - improvement of the intestinal mucosal barrier [5] Probiotics ensure the regulation of intestinal permeability, tighten the connection between individual enterocytes, against the background of which toxins and other “unwanted” bacteria do not easily pass into the blood, which accordingly reduces endotoxemia[8] By increasing the production of Glucagon Like Peptide 1 (GLP1) by the intestine, as is known in type 2 diabetes, the level of incretins in the body decreases, in turn, incretins are glucose regulators. According to the existing data, certain types of probiotics have the effect of affecting incretins, namely they indirectly increase the level of GLP1 in the blood [11] by increasing the amount of insulin released from the β -cells of the pancreas. Although the functioning of the pancreas, i.e., the production of insulin, is not impaired in type 2 diabetes mellitus, on the contrary, in many cases we find hyperinsulinemia, it is believed that the high blood sugar level over a long period of time has a depressing effect on the functioning of the pancreas. Increasing insulin production plays a leading role in the process of regulating glycemia due to the decrease in plasma glucose concentration.

We can conclude that the improvement of microflora in patients with type 2 diabetes has a positive effect on the reduction of glyated hemoglobin, which is a step forward in improving the quality of life of these patients.

References

1. IDF Diabetes atlas - <https://diabetesatlas.org/>
2. Jeremiah J Faith 1.- The long-term stability of the human gut microbiota. *Science*. 2013 Jul 5;341(6141):1237439.
3. Katamadze N., Kandashvili T., Metreveli D., Gordeladze D. – The role of gut Microbiota in patients with type 2 Diabetes and insulin resistance.
4. Kaitlyn Oliphant & Emma Allen-Vercoc: Macronutrient metabolism by the human gut microbiome: major fermentation by-products and their impact on host health. *Microbiome* volume 7, Article number: 91 (2019).
5. M.A. McArdle, O.M. Finucane, R.M. Connaughton, et al., Mechanisms of obesity-induced inflammation and insulin resistance: insights into the emerging role of nutritional strategies, *Frontiers in Endocrinology* 4 (2013) 52.
6. M. Diamant, E.E. Blaak, W.M. Vos de, Do nutrient–gut–microbiota interactions play a role in human obesity, insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes? *Obesity Reviews* 12 (2011) 272–281.
7. M.G. Gareau, P.M. Sherman, W.A. Walker, Probiotics and the gut microbiota in intestinal health and disease, *Nature Reviews Gastroenterology & Hepatology* 7 (2010) 503–514.
8. M.Y. Donath, Inflammation as a sensor of metabolic stress in obesity and type 2 diabetes, *Endocrinology* 152 (2011) 4005–4006.
9. Shamanadze A. Kandashvili T. - Impact of Intestinal Microbiota on Quality of Life (QoL) of Hemodialysis Patients
10. Shamanadze A, Kandashvili T. Tchokhonelidze I. – Assessment of quality of life if hemodialysis patients by BY MWQOLI METHOD
11. Z. Asemi, S. Jazayeri, M. Najafi, et al., Effects of daily consumption of probiotic yoghurt on inflammatory factors in pregnant women: a randomized controlled trial, *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences* 14 (2011)476–482.